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Financial Literacy And Youth Entrepreneurship In South East Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study analyzed the financial literacy and its impact on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria. The objective of the study was to; ascertain the effect of financial knowledge, financial behaviour and financial expertise on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria. Three research hypotheses are formulated in line with the above objectives of the study. Descriptive survey design method was used; Structured questionnaire were use to gather information from the population. The population of the study is made of youths from age 20-39 in South East zone of Nigeria, which is 50,222,32 target population. It comprises of all the youths in South East Nigeria, while the sample size is 399 were gotten through taro yamane formular. The researcher distributes three hundred and ninety-nine (399) questionnaires but only three hundred and seventy-three (373) copies of questionnaire were retrieved. Correlation and t-test method of data analysis was used to test the hypotheses. The finding of the study shows that; Financial knowledge has significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria. Financial behaviour has significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria. The study recommends that Banks should develop a mechanism (expansion of financial knowledge facilities) to educate and expand the financial knowledge of the youths who are entrepreneurs. Banks in Southeast should conduct account opening programme specifically for young entrepreneurs to expand their experience of financial behavior.

Keywords: financial literacy, financial knowledge, financial behaviour, financial expertise, youth entrepreneurship

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In today's world of business, financial literacy has attracted increasing attention mostly in the developed, developing and underdeveloped countries due to its role in financial decision. For instance, in the

developed countries of the world such as United States of America (USA), financial literacy is key to business at all level. This led the USA government in January 2008 for the establishment of a president's advisory council on financial literacy tasked to improve financial education at all levels of the economy. Developing economies have also not been left behind; countries like, Nigeria, Malaysia and South Africa have set up programmes that are aimed at increasing financial literacy (Hilgert & Hogath, 2018).

Financial literacy encompasses the knowledge and skill required by individual to function effectively in the money economy and make informed judgments in respect to their own and their family circumstances (Emeka 2021). The need for financial literacy among entrepreneurs and business owners has henceforth become a subject of interest in both developed and developing economies of the world (Hilgert & Hogath, 2018). Though it might not be an absolute state, it enables individuals to be able to respond effectively to ever changing personal, social and economic circumstances. Financial literacy is hypothesized to be a major determinant of the firm's success or failure of every business. It is for this reason, many countries have created task forces to study and evaluate the level of the financial literacy of their citizens as it affects businesses (Alessie *et al.*, 2019). Drexler, Fischer, and Schoar (2014) posited that entrepreneurs usually suffer from insufficient financial literacy to make the complex financial decisions they face. This is unfortunate, since according to Oseifuah (2017), financial literacy among youth entrepreneur contributes meaningfully to their entrepreneurship skills. Entrepreneurs who want to grow, need to have confident of their finances, as well be adequately informed (Kotzè & Smit, 2018).

Adequate financial management skill which comes with financial literacy is paramount for businesses to grow, it also provides entrepreneurs with empowerment and information to evaluate financial products and make informed decisions, facilitates proper debt management which puts the business in a better credit-worthy position (Emeka 2022). Financial literacy is a critical factor to the growth of any business venture. Despite its necessity for the success of an entrepreneur it has not been given any importance in research in Nigeria, rather it has been confused with entrepreneurial education or knowledge from time to time.

The problem with financial literacy is that most entrepreneurs with a low level of financial literacy do not give serious thoughts to keeping proper accounting records, and this inadequacy and ineffectiveness of their accounting system and accounting processes have been responsible for the untimely collapse of a most of them. They rather recruit unskilled personnel who cannot keep proper records to take charge of accounting activities (Ezejiofor *et al.*, 2014). Thus, resulting in unreliable accounting records and this makes it difficult for the entrepreneur to woo investors successfully or access credit facilities at the banks, since the books cannot reveal the condition or financial state of the business (Jacobs, & Arinze, 2021). This invariably has resulted into a situation where enterprenuerial operators cannot capture adequately their business profits. This is because in the process of calculating profit, financial data are assembled in a way that cannot help make informed financial judgment and decision taking. These financial data cannot be assembled without adequate financial literacy. In addition to the above problems are lack of awareness of financial risk and opportunities, reckless expenditure, use of business funds for personal transactions, limited access to bank credit facilities and insurance policies and all is often as a result of lack of financial knowledge.

1.2 Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to ascertain financial literacy and its impact on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria. The specific objectives are:

- 1) To ascertain the effect of financial knowledge on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria.
- 2) To determine the effect of financial behaviour on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria.
- 3) To determine the effect of financial expertise on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

Financial Literacy

Financial literacy is defined as the level at which an individual understands important financial concepts with the knowledge and boldness to his/her finances by making the right short-term decisions, making financial plans on a long-term basis while being mindful of life's uncertainties and the dynamic situation of the economy (Remund, 2010). Lusardi and Mitchell (2017) defined financial literacy as the process by which financial consumers/investors improve their understanding of financial products and concepts and through information, instruction, and/or objective advice, develop the skills and confidence to become more aware of financial risks and opportunities to make informed choices, to know where to go for help and to take other effective actions to improve their financial well-being.

In the same vein, Dahmen & Rodríguez (2014) described financial literacy as the capability of a business owner to assimilate and properly use financial reports to make sound and technical financial decisions for the wellbeing of the business. For Valladares (2020), financial literacy surmounts as knowledge about earnings, expenditures, savings, investments and long term financial planning. Financial literacy refers to the knowledge of money and financial products that people can apply to financial choices in order to make informed decisions about how to handle their finances (Basu, 2016). It includes the ability to make informed judgments and to take effective decision regarding financial matters (Worthington, 2015).

Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2018) argued that financial literacy must involve not only the investors but also the customers, both having the knowledge of financial products and concepts and their ability to consider financial risks in their decision making and to make other effective actions to improve their financial levels. Financial literacy is essential in helping individuals to identify vital financial issues and behaviors that support effective management of financial resources (Hilgert & Hogath, 2016).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is proposed by Ajzen (1991). TPB is a psychological theory that connects beliefs to behaviour. The theory contains three core components which are, attitude toward the behaviour, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control. Attitude toward the behaviour refers to the degree of an individual perceives things good or bad. Subjective norms mean the particular belief is accepted or disapproved by the society. Perceived behavioural control describes how people perceive the ease or difficulty of performing of a behaviour. The greater of behavioural intention when there is sufficient of resources and ability to control barriers to behaviours. TPB can be used as a guideline for measuring entrepreneurial intention among university students.

TPB is a tool that is used to explain the steps of starting a new business venture whereby it views behavioural aim as a main cause of planned behaviour (Ajzen, 1991; Ajzen & Fishbein, 1977). Intentions are the most suitable predictor of any planned behaviour which including entrepreneurship (Krueger *et al.*, 2000). It is significant to understand the antecedents of intentions in order to have a good understanding of the intended behaviour. However, research addressing causes on entrepreneurial intention among students is very seldom (Hoda *et al.*, 2020; Lüthje & Franke, 2003; Wang & Wong, 2004). An individual's intention to behave entrepreneurially will have high self-efficacy in order to achieve goals (Zhao & Wibowo, 2021). Therefore, TPB is also applied in this research to investigate the entrepreneurial intention among university students. The first component of TPB which is attitude is related to the financial attitude and financial knowledge in this study. Attitude of students towards financial management or money is investigated to evaluate the influence of financial attitude on entrepreneurial intention.

2.3 Empirical Studies

Muhammed, *et al.* (2024) examined the influence of financial literacy and entrepreneurship training on entrepreneurship intentions of PLWDs in Nigeria. Using a descriptive survey research, the population comprises all the PLWDs in the North West region of Nigeria, out of which a sample of 210 were

conveniently surveyed using questionnaire. With the help of SPSS, the data collected was analyzed using descriptive, correlation, and regression. The results revealed that entrepreneurship training was significant on entrepreneurship intention of the PLWDs, while financial literacy was not significant on entrepreneurship intentions. The study concludes that, while financial literacy does not determine entrepreneurship intention of the PLWDs, entrepreneurship training does.

Ibitomi, et. al. (2024) examined financial literacy and performance of SMEs in Abuja, Nigeria. The study used survey method in achieving the objectives through the use of primary data collection. Questionnaire were administered to 550 respondents in all the six areas council of Abuja, Nigeria while 469 was usable and analyzed for the study. The data analysis method used was multiple regressions due to the nature of the data collected. The findings from the study revealed that respondents have adequate financial knowledge of their various businesses as such impact positively on their businesses in Abuja,

Biia, Mutai and Rotich (2024) established the role of Financial Literacy on the development of sustainable business ideas and innovations. The population of interests was the business enterprises run by youthful entrepreneurs across various sectors of business in Bomet Municipality located in Bomet County; Kenya. The study used primary data with a sample size of 473 respondents which achieved 100% response rate, with male response of 53% and 47% female. The measures of central tendency, measures of dispersion and Regression model were used to find out the relationship and correlation of the variables.

Akinyede, (2023) investigated the level of awareness of financial literacy among selected SSEs in south western Nigeria. The Study made use of primary data collected through the use of a structured questionnaire. Necessary sampling method was adopted in the study and snowballing method was used to administer both physical and electronic questionnaire. The result showed that the t-statistic probability strongly suggests that all three coefficients, Manager's Literacy (ML), Technical Competence (TC) and Firm size (FS) have a positive and significant effect on Entrepreneurship performance (EP) with P-value of 0.0226, 0.0372 and 0.0316 respectively. In conclusion the success of a company can be significantly impacted by financial literacy. Employees in businesses that are financially literate are more likely to react to changes in the market and make choices that will boost the company's performance.

Arshiya, (2023) explored the impact of financial literacy and financial inclusion on the entrepreneurial inclination of undergraduate students in Bangalore, focusing on autonomous institutions. The study identifies factors influencing the success of Micro, Small, and Medium-sized Enterprises (MSMEs) entrepreneurs in Bangalore, focusing on variables such as financial literacy, awareness of financial inclusion, and entrepreneurial willingness among undergraduate students. Key findings indicate a strong awareness of financial risks among students, with a need for increased knowledge about funding sources.

Ifechukwu-jacobs, C.J & Atueyi, C.L (2025). Material management and productivity of Nigeria bottling appraised the material management and productivity of Nigerian Bottling Company. The population of the study was 288 staff. While two hundred and seventy (270) questionnaires were retrieved. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed, Planning has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 14.027. Material procurement has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 33.048. Logistic has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 9.418. Stock and waste control has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha.

METHODOLOGY

3.1: Research Design

This study will employed survey research design. Survey Design as it is used in a pure research context refers to the total constructional plan or structure of the research framework. The instrument use for data collection was structured questionnaire.

3.2: Sources of Data

The primary source of data will be used in this study because of the variables that are used in the study. Questionnaire will be used to collect data from the youth of the selected state

3.3: Population of the Study

The population of the study is made of youths from age 20-39 in South East zone of Nigeria

s/n	State	Staff strength
1	Anambra State	1323558
2	Imo State	1203817
4	Ebonyi State	611391
5	Enugu State	997746
6	Abia State	885720
7	Total	5022232

Sources: www.city population.ed. retrieved 20 Oct, 2024

3.4 Determination of Sample Size.

Taro Yamane formula will be used to determine the Sample size. The formula is given as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where

n= Sample size of the study=

N = Population

1 = Constant value

e = Error margin assumed to be (5%)

Applying this formula, we have

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{5022232}{1+5022232(5\%)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{5022232}{1+5022232(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{5022232}{12556.58}$$

$$n = \frac{5022232}{12556.58}$$

Sample size = 399.37941 apprx 399

Sample Frame

The proportionate distribution of the sample by state is shown in the table below:

s/n	State	Population	Proportional distribution of sample size	Sample size per State
1	Anambra State	1323558	399/5022232x1323558	105
2	Imo State	1203817	399/5022232x1203817	95
4	Ebonyi State	611391	399/5022232x611391	49
5	Enugu State	997746	399/5022232x997746	79
6	Abia State	885720	399/5022232x885720	71
	Total	5022232		399

3.5: Method of Data Analysis.

Statistics such as frequency count and percentages table will be used in the analysis of research questions while research hypotheses will be tested using correlation analysis and simple regression analysis. The research hypotheses will be assessed at 0.05 level of significance. Analysis will be carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

4.1 Distributions of Questionnaire

Table 4.1.1 Information on Distribution of Questionnaire

s/n	Options	No of Respondents	Percentage %
1	Questionnaire Distributed	399	100%
2	Questionnaire Returned	381	95%
3	Questionnaire Completed	373	93%
4	Questionnaire Not Duly Completed	5	1%
5	Questionnaire Missing	3	0.7%

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1 showed that a total number of three hundred and ninety-nine (399) copies of questionnaire were distributed to the respondents, three hundred and eighty-one (381) copies which represented 95% were returned, three hundred, seventy-three (373) which represent 93% where completed and five (5) copies which represented 1% were not duly completed by the respondents, while three (3) copies which represented only 0.7% of the total questionnaire were missing. Hence, the analyses for this study were based on the three hundred and seventy-three (373) copies which represented 93% of the sample population.

4.2 Test of Statement of Hypotheses

HO₁: Financial knowledge has no significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria.

HO₂: Financial behaviour has no significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria.

HO₃: Financial expertise has no significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria.

4.2.1 Hypothesis one

HO₁: Financial knowledge has no significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria.

Correlations

		YET	FINK		
Spearman's rho	YET	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.540**	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	
		N	373	373	
	Bootstrap ^b	Bias	.000	.002	
		Std. Error	.000	.044	
		BCa 95% Confidence Interval	Lower	.	.255
			Upper	.	.447
	FINK	Correlation Coefficient	.540**	1.000	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	
		N	373	373	
Bootstrap ^b		Bias	.002	.000	
		Std. Error	.044	.000	
		BCa 95% Confidence Interval	Lower	.255	.
			Upper	.447	.

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

b. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 373 bootstrap samples

Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower				Upper
Pair 1	YET - FINK	.38070	1.10222	.05707	.26847	.49292	6.671	372	.000

Table 1a indicates the relationship between the independent variable Financial knowledge and the dependent variable youth entrepreneurship. At a 0.05 level of significant, 95% confidence level interval ranges between . .447 and . .49292 at the upper case, and also .255 and .26847 at the lower case, with a 2 tailed test of sample distribution showing the critical area in a distribution. The spearman correlation coefficient shows a value of 54% which shows a high correlation coefficient between the dependent and independent variable. This further portrays the high goodness of fit of the model

Model 1= $YET = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FINK + \mu$

Table 1 indicates the difference in mean value (.38070) and standard deviation (1.10222) for the extent of relationship that existed between the variables included in the group. The single group variables in model one of the hypotheses are represented by YET & FINK (youth entrepreneurship & financial knowledge). However, the paired sample t-test showed that youth entrepreneurship level increased significantly when financial knowledge is adhere to. A t-test value of financial knowledge is said to be significantly high when it is above or equal to 2 (t-value > 2), but when the t-value is less than 2 (t-value < 2), it is concluded that the perceived outcome within the paired sample has no significant relationship. In conclusion to this result, the t-value was obtained at 6.671 which is significantly high. The study therefore concluded that there is a significantly positive relationship between financial knowledge and youth entrepreneurship in South East of Nigeria

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, otherwise, reject.

Decision: We reject the null hypothesis, since the p-value is 0.000** which is less than the critical value 0.05, this study reveals that Financial knowledge has significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria

4.2.2 Hypothesis Two

HO₂: Financial behaviour has no significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria.

Correlations

		YET	FINB		
Spearman's rho	YET	Correlation Coefficient	1.000		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.374**		
		N	.000		
	Bootstrap ^b	Bias	Std. Error	.000	
			BCa 95% Confidence Interval	.000	
		Lower	Upper	.441	
			Upper	.598	
		FINB	Correlation Coefficient	.374**	1.000
			Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
			N	373	373
Bootstrap ^b	Bias		.000	.000	
	Std. Error		.041	.000	
BCa 95% Confidence Interval	Lower	.441	.		
	Upper	.598	.		

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

b. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 373 bootstrap samples

Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	YET - FINB	.22788	1.21994	.06317	.10367	.35209	3.608	372	.000

Table 2 indicates the relationship between the independent variable Financial Behaviour (FINB) and the dependent variable Youth Entrepreneurship (YET). At a 0.05 level of significant, 95% confidence level interval ranges between .598 and .35209 at the upper case, and also .441 and .10367 at the lower case, with a 2 tailed test of sample distribution showing the critical area in a distribution. The spearman correlation coefficient shows a value of 0.37%, which shows a moderate correlation coefficient between the dependent and independent variable. This further portrays the goodness of fit of the model

Model 2= $YET = \beta_0 + \beta_1FINB + \mu$

Table 2 indicates the difference in mean value (.22788) and standard deviation (1.21994) for the extent of relationship that existed between the variables included in the group. The single group variables in model two of the hypotheses are represented by YET & FINB (Youth Entrepreneurship and Financial Behaviour).

However, the paired sample t-test showed that Youth Entrepreneurship level increased significantly when the perceived Financial Behaviour was adopted. A t-test value of Financial Behaviour is said to be significantly high when it is above or equal 2 (t-value > 2.00), but when the t-value is less than 2.00 (t-value < 2.00), it is concluded that the Financial Behaviour within the paired sample has no significant relationship. In conclusion to this result, the t-value was obtained at 3.608 which is significant high. The study therefore concluded that there is a significantly high positive relationship between financial behaviour and youth entrepreneurship in South East of Nigeria

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, otherwise, reject.

Decision: We reject the null hypothesis, since the p-value is 0.000** which is less than the critical value 0.05, this study reveals that Financial behaviour has significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria

4.2.3 Hypothesis Three

H0₃: Financial expertise has no significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria.

Correlations

				YET	FINE	
Spearman's rho	YET	Correlation Coefficient		1.000	.458**	
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.	.000	
		N		373	373	
		Bootstrap ^b	Bias		.000	-.002
			Std. Error		.000	.044
			95% Confidence Interval	Lower	1.000	.369
		Upper		1.000	.536	
	FINE	Correlation Coefficient		.458**	1.000	
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.	
		N		373	373	
		Bootstrap ^b	Bias		-.002	.000
			Std. Error		.044	.000
			95% Confidence Interval	Lower	.369	1.000
		Upper		.536	1.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

b. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 373 bootstrap samples

Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	YET - FINE	.36729	1.80552	.09349	.18346	.55112	3.929	372	.000

Table 3 indicates the relationship between the independent variable Financial expertise (FINE) and the dependent variable youth entrepreneurship. At a 0.05 level of significant, 95% confidence level interval ranging between 0. 536 and 0. .55112 at the upper case, and also .369 and .18346 at the lower case, with a 2 tailed test of sample distribution showing the critical area in a distribution. The spearman correlation coefficient shows a value of 45% which shows a high correlation coefficient between the dependent and independent variable. This further portrays the high goodness of fit of the model

Model 3= $YET = \beta_0 + B_1FINE + \mu$

Table 3 indicates the difference in mean value (.36729) and standard deviation (1.80552) for the extent of relationship that existed between the variables included in the group. The single group variables in model two of the hypotheses are represented by YET & FINE (youth entrepreneurship and financial expertise).

However, the paired sample t-test showed that youth entrepreneurship level increased significantly when the effective financial expertise was adopted. A t-test value of S financial expertise is said to be significantly high when it is above or equal to 2 (t-value > 2.00), but when the t-value is less than 2.00 (t-value < 2.00), it is concluded that the perceived outcome within the paired sample has no significant relationship. In conclusion to this result, the t-value was obtained at 3.929 which is significant high. The study therefore concluded that there is significantly high positive relationship between financial expertise and youth entrepreneurship in South East of Nigeria

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, otherwise, reject.

Decision: We reject the null hypothesis, since the p-value is 0.000** which is less than the critical value 0.05, this study reveals that Financial expertise has significant positive effect on youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, financial literacy plays a vital role in promoting youth entrepreneurship in South East Nigeria. By understanding financial concepts, such as budgeting, saving, investing, and risk management, young entrepreneurs can make more informed decisions, access capital, and grow their businesses. However, financial literacy is not widely taught in schools and universities in South East Nigeria, resulting in a lack of knowledge and skills among many young entrepreneurs. To address this gap, government agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and financial institutions should collaborate to promote financial education and support youth entrepreneurship initiatives. Based on the research findings and the conclusions drawn thereof, the following recommendations were made: Banks should develop a mechanism (expansion of financial knowledge facilities) to educate and expand the financial knowledge of the youths who are entrepreneurs. Banks in Southeast should conduct account opening programme specifically for young entrepreneurs to expand their experience of financial behavior. There is need for banks to develop synergy that will produce in-bank or in-business financial expertise for young entrepreneurs on financial account reporting and budgeting

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